

[GRASP/GAPMAP-0] Quality Assessment Summary

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REFERENCE

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

- RD-1. EDAP Best Practice Guidelines, EDAP.REP.001, v2.2, 6th December 2022.
- RD-2. Earth Observation Mission Quality Assessment Framework - Atmospheric Guidelines, EDAP.REP.061, v0.1, October 2021
- RD-3. Dubovik, O., Fuertes, D., Litvinov, P., Lopatin, A., Lapyonok, T., Dubovik, I., ... & Federspiel, C. (2021). A comprehensive description of multi-term LSM for applying multiple a priori constraints in problems of atmospheric remote sensing: GRASP algorithm, concept, and applications. *Frontiers in Remote Sensing*, 2, 706851.
- RD-4. Chen, C., Dubovik, O., Fuertes, D., Litvinov, P., Lapyonok, T., Lopatin, A., ... & Federspiel, C. (2020). Validation of GRASP algorithm product from POLDER/PARASOL data and assessment of multi-angular polarimetry potential for aerosol monitoring. *Earth System Science Data*, 12(4), 3573-3620.
- RD-5. Zhang, X., Li, L., Chen, C., Chen, X., Dubovik, O., Derimian, Y., ... & Zhang, X. (2021). Validation of the aerosol optical property products derived by the GRASP/Component approach from multi-angular polarimetric observations. *Atmospheric Research*, 263, 105802.
- RD-6. Chen, C., Dubovik, O., Litvinov, P., Fuertes, D., Lopatin, A., Lapyonok, T., ... & Bojkov, B. (2022). Properties of aerosol and surface derived from OLCI/Sentinel-3A using GRASP approach: Retrieval development and preliminary validation. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 280, 113142.
- RD-7. Herrera, M. E., Dubovik, O., Torres, B., Lapyonok, T., Fuertes, D., Lopatin, A., ... & Ristori, P. R. (2022). Estimates of remote sensing retrieval errors by the GRASP algorithm: application to ground-based observations, concept and validation. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 15(20), 6075-6126.
- RD-8. EDAP+ Assessment - Introduction of GAPMAP Jan 29th, 2025 - internal presentation.
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- RD-12. Holben, B. N., Eck, T. F., Slutsker, I. A., Tanre, D., Buis, J. P., Setzer, A., ... & Smirnov, A. (1998). AERONET—A federated instrument network and data archive for aerosol characterization. *Remote sensing of environment*, 66(1), 1-16.
- RD-13. Mira, M., Weiss, M., Baret, F., Courault, D., Hagolle, O., Gallego-Elvira, B., & Olioso, A. (2015). The MODIS (collection V006) BRDF/albedo product MCD43D: Temporal course evaluated over agricultural landscape. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 170, 216-228.
- RD-14. Aeronet V3 AOD L1.5 and L2 description: https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/new_web/Documents/AERONET_V3_AOD.pdf
- RD-15. Giles, D. M., Sinyuk, A., Sorokin, M. G., Schafer, J. S., Smirnov, A., Slutsker, I., ... & Lyapustin, A. I. (2019). Advancements in the Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) Version 3 database—automated near-real-time quality control algorithm with improved cloud screening for Sun photometer aerosol optical depth (AOD) measurements. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 12(1), 169-209.
- RD-16. Di Girolamo, L. (2003). Generalizing the definition of the bi-directional reflectance distribution function. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 88(4), 479-482.
- RD-17. Maignan, F., Bréon, F. M., & Lacaze, R. (2004). Bidirectional reflectance of Earth targets: Evaluation of analytical models using a large set of spaceborne measurements with emphasis on the Hot Spot. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 90(2), 210-220.
- RD-18. Lucht, W., Schaaf, C. B., & Strahler, A. H. (2002). An algorithm for the retrieval of albedo from space using semiempirical BRDF models. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote sensing*, 38(2), 977-998.

GLOSSARY

AERONET: AErosol RObotic NETwork

AOI: Area of Interest

ATBD: Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document

EDAP: Earthnet Data Assessment Pilot

EO: Earth Observation

ESA: European Space Agency

GRASP: Generalized Retrieval of Aerosol and Surface Properties (algorithm)

LEO: Low Earth Orbit

MM: Maturity Matrix

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

GRASP GAPMAP-0 is a multi-angle, multispectral polarimeter launched in 2023 meant as orbit demonstrator for future constellation. GAPMAP-0 provides 60 measurements per pixel, resulting from 4 wavelengths (440, 550, 670, 870 nm), 5 different angles of acquisition (2 backwards, nadir, 2 frontwards) and 3 different polarization states (I,U,V Stokes parameters). Table 1.1 summarizes the characteristic of GAMPMP-0 and the future constellation. Through the application of GRASP algorithm [RD-3, RD-4] to the Level 1 data acquired by GAPMAP, the aerosol and surface properties can be retrieved (Level 2). Table 1.2 reports the list of preliminary outputs generated by GRASP algorithm at the current state.

Figure 1.1 GRASP GAPMAP sensor.

Figure 1.2 GRASP GAPMAP timeline for constellation development.

Table 1.1 GRASP GAPMAP constellation sensor specification.

GRASP GAPMAP Constellation specification	
Wavelengths	440, 550, 670, 870 nm
Calibration	<i>Full onboard calibration; solar + moon; ground targets; satellite comparisons.</i>
Nadir pixel resolution	<i>0.58 km</i>
Nadir binned resolution	<i>2.32 km</i>
Cross track swath	<i>77 deg (1070km @650km orbit)</i>
Along track swath	<i>105.2 deg</i>
Hyper-Angular Sampling	<i>Up to 60 angles</i>
Angular sampling	<i>Hyperangular</i>
Satellite volume	<i><1.5U</i>

Table 1.2 GRASP GAPMAP-0 Level 2 preliminary products.

Variable Name	Definition	Units	Dimensions
Aerosol_optical_depth	Aerosols optical depth per mode	Unitless	(t,y,x,band,aerosol_mode)
Aerosol_single_scattering_albedo	Single scattering albedo of aerosols per mode	Unitless	(t,y,x,band,aerosol_mode)
Aerosol_absorption_optical_depth	Absorption optical depth of aerosols per mode	Unitless	(t,y,x,band,aerosol_mode)
Aerosol_optical_depth_total	Total aerosols optical depth	Unitless	(t,y,x,band)
Aerosol_single_scattering_albedo_total	Total single scattering albedo aerosols	Unitless	(t,y,x,band)
Aerosol_absorption_optical_depth_total	Total absorption optical depth of aerosols	Unitless	(t,y,x,band)
Aerosol_angstrom_exponent		Unitless	(t,y,x)
Surface_water_cox_munk_iso_1	First Cox-Munk water surface reflectance parameter (water leaving reflectance)	Unitless	(t,y,x,band)
Surface_water_cox_munk_iso_2	Second Cox-Munk water surface reflectance parameter foam fraction)	Unitless	(t,y,x)
Surface_water_cox_munk_iso_3	Third Cox-Munk water surface reflectance parameter (facet slope)	Unitless	(t,y,x)
Surface_land_brdf_rossli_isotropic	Ross-Li BRDF isotropic component for land surfaces	Unitless	(t,y,x,band)
Surface_land_brdf_rossli_volumetric_normalized	Ross-Li BRDF volumetric component normalized for land	Unitless	(t,y,x)
Surface_land_brdf_rossli_geometric_normalized	Ross-Li BRDF geometric component normalized for land	Unitless	(t,y,x)
Surface_land_polarized_maignan_breon_1	Maignan-Breon polarized reflectance for land	Unitless	(t,y,x)
Surface_directional_hemispherical_reflectance	Directional hemispherical reflectance of the surface (DHR)	Unitless	(t,y,x,band)
Surface_isotropical_bihemispherical_reflectance	Isotropic bihemispherical reflectance of the surface (BHR)	Unitless	(t,y,x,band)
Absolute_residual	Absolute residual of modeled vs observed values	Unitless	(t,y,x,noise)
Relative_residual	Relative residual pf modelled vs observed values	Unitless	(t,y,x,noise)
Number_of_iterations	Number of iterations performed during computation	Unitless	(t,y,x)

1.1 Cal/Val Maturity Matrices

1.1.1 Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

Data Provider Documentation Review			Validation Summary
Product Information	Metrology	Product Generation	
Product Details	Measurement Validation Method		
Availability & Accessibility	Measurement Validation Results Compliance		
Product Format, Flags & Metadata	Retrieval Algorithm	Geometric Validation Method	
User Documentation	Geometric Validation Results Compliance		
Ancillary Data			

Key
Not Assessed
Not Assessable
Basic
Good
Excellent
Ideal
Not Public

Figure 1.3 - Summary Matrix Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

1.1.2 Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

GAPMAP-0 AOD and BRDF Detailed Validation				Key
Measurement		Geometric		
GAPMAP-0 AOD and BRDF vs MODIS #1 Method	GAPMAP-0 AOD and BRDF vs MODIS #1 Results Compliance	GAPMAP-0 AOD and BRDF vs MODIS #1 Method	GAPMAP-0 AOD and BRDF vs MODIS #1 Results Compliance	Not Assessed
	GAPMAP-0 AOD vs AERONET #2 Results Compliance	GAPMAP-0 AOD vs AERONET #2 Method	GAPMAP-0 AOD vs AERONET #2 Results Compliance	Not Assessable
GAPMAP-0 AOD vs AERONET #2 Method	GAPMAP-0 AOD vs AERONET #2 Results Compliance	GAPMAP-0 AOD vs AERONET #2 Method	GAPMAP-0 AOD vs AERONET #2 Results Compliance	Basic
				Good
				Excellent
				Ideal
				Not Public

Figure 1.4 – Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

2. DATA PROVIDER DOCUMENTATION REVIEW

2.1 Product Information

Product Details	
Grade: Ideal	
Justification	<i>All required information available.</i>
Product Name	<i>GRASP GAPMAP L2 Aerosol and Surface Properties</i>
Sensor Name	<i>GAPMAP-0</i>
Sensor Type	<i>Multi-angle, multispectral polarimeter</i>
Mission Type	<i>In-Orbit Demonstrator for the future constellation</i>
Mission Orbit	<i>Sun-synchronous Low Earth Orbit (~500 km altitude)</i>
Product Version Number	<i>V0.3 and V0.4</i>
Product ID	<i>GRASP_GAPMAP-0_L2_AER+SUR</i>
Processing level of product	<i>Level 2</i>
Measured Quantity Name	<i>Aerosol optical depth (AOD), Single scattering albedo (SSA), Bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF), accessory parameters</i>
Measured Quantity Units	<i>Unitless</i>
Stated Measurement Quality	<i>Preliminary initial validation shows reasonable consistency with reference data; full quantitative quality assessment is ongoing and further improvements are planned.</i>
Spatial Resolution	<i>Nominal resolution at nadir 300m, binned at 2.3 km resolution for L2 products.</i>
Spatial Coverage	<i>400 targeted captures distributed globally</i>
Temporal Resolution	<i>~3-day revisit time (depending on target latitude)</i>
Temporal Coverage	<i>5 May 2023 – 26 March 2024</i>
Point of Contact	support@grasp-earth.com
Product locator (DOI/URL)	<i>N.A. product not yet publicly available</i>
Conditions for access and use	<i>Restricted access through registration - internal use for validation and algorithm development</i>
Limitations on public access	<i>Product not yet accessible</i>
Product Abstract	<i>The GAPMAP-0 instrument is a multi-angle polarimeter developed by GRASP-Earth. It was successfully launched in April 2023 as part of the Adler-2 satellite mission. GAPMAP-0 is the initial deployment in a planned constellation of 10 CubeSats, scheduled for launch between 2026 and 2030. The L2 products analysed are to be considered a test version comprising variables for studying aerosol properties and surface reflectance.</i>

Availability & Accessibility	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<i>The products analysed is a test version, not available to the public.</i>
Compliant with FAIR principles	<i>Partially compliant. The product analysed is correlated with rich set of metadata. Findable: not public. Accessible: not public. Interoperable: yes, standard data format. Reusable: PUM provided with data description.</i>
Data Management Plan	<i>Not available</i>
Availability Status	<i>Not public</i>

Product Format	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<i>Data exist in a documented standard file format. Non-standard naming conventions used. Includes a good set of documented metadata and data flags.</i>
Product File Format	<i>netCDF4</i>
Metadata Conventions	<i>No but Metadata variables are easy to understand. (Self-explained variable names)</i>
Analysis Ready Data?	<i>No</i>

User Documentation		
Grade: Good		
Justification	<i>Some PUG and ATBD-type information available. These may be formal documents or from multiple sources. Documentation is up-to-date. Sensibility studies and validation are envisaged for future products. When these parts are added to the documentation the grade will become excellent.</i>	
<i>Document</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>QA4ECV Compliant</i>
Product User Guide	<i>GAPMAP_GRASP_AOD+BRDF_PUM_v0.1.0</i>	<i>Partially compliant</i>
ATBD	<i>GAPMAP_GRASP_AOD+BRDF_ATBD_v0.2.0</i>	<i>Partially compliant</i>

2.2 Metrology

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Pre-flight and post-launch measurement calibration & characterisation documents cover most important aspects of instrument behaviour at a level of quality to be judged fit for purpose.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GAPMAP_GRASP_AOD+BRDF_ATBD_v0.2.0

Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Geometric calibration & characterisation covers most important aspects of instrument behaviour at a level of quality to be judged fit for purpose.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GAPMAP_GRASP_AOD+BRDF_ATBD_v0.2.0

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Traceability chain documented identifying most important steps and sources of uncertainty. Uncertainty tree diagram not present. L1 radiometric measurement uncertainty is a-priori
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GAPMAP_GRASP_AOD+BRDF_ATBD_v0.2.0

Uncertainty Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	No GUM approach but comparison to measurements by other sensors is performed. Most important sources of uncertainty are included.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GAPMAP_GRASP_AOD+BRDF_ATBD_v0.2.0

Calibration Algorithm	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Calibration algorithm documented. The algorithm is not reported in the L2 ATBD but generally described in the text. Algorithm judged “fit for purpose” in terms of the mission’s stated performance for most expected use cases.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GAPMAP_GRASP_AOD+BRDF_ATBD_v0.2.0
Ancillary Data	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	Land/Water Mask applied. Well documented with clear references in the ATBD.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GAPMAP_GRASP_AOD+BRDF_ATBD_v0.2.0

2.3 Product Generation

Geometric Processing	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Geometric processing documented. Retrieval algorithm is not reported in the L2 ATBD but generally described in the text. Confidence in the calibration quality is considered sufficient.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GAPMAP_GRASP_AOD+BRDF_ATBD_v0.2.0

Retrieval Algorithm	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	Retrieval algorithm documented. Retrieval algorithm “fit for purpose” it represents the state-of-the art for the aerosol properties retrieval. It is documented in several scientific publications.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GAPMAP_GRASP_AOD+BRDF_ATBD_v0.2.0

Mission-Specific Processing	
Grade: Not assessable	

Justification	<i>No addition processing steps applied.</i>
Reference	<i>GAPMAP_GRASP_AOD+BRDF_ATBD_v0.2.0</i>

3. DETAILED VALIDATION

This section summarizes the results of the cross-comparison of GAPMAP data with selected reference dataset. We analysed two datasets that at this stage are meant for internal use only, one from V0.3 and the other from V0.4. GRASP has provided four scenes for V0.3 over Arabian and Indian regions, and ten scenes for V0.4, over the Arabic peninsula, Italy, north Africa, and Indian regions. Three scenes are common to both versions. Scenes have been acquired between December 2023 and March 2024. V0.4 presents improvements with respect to V0.3: stray-light correction, sun glint mask, and improved geolocation and information regarding observation geometry.

The GAPMAP L2 products comprises variables related to the aerosols and air quality properties, and surface optical properties. In this work we analysed two main GAPMAP variables: total aerosol optical depth at 550 nm (*aerosol_optical_depth_total*) and Ross-Li Bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) isotropic component for land surfaces (*surface_land_brdf_rossli_isotropic*).

The total aerosol optical depth has been compared with MODIS data of collection MOD_04L2 [RD-9] selecting the analogue variable at the same wavelength of GAPMAP, 550 nm (*AOD_550_Dark_Target_Deep_Blue_Combined*) [RD-10] with ground-based measurement from Aeronet network [RD-12]. The selected variable contains the results of the two main algorithms employed by MODIS, Dark Target and Deep Blue, applied mainly to ocean and land pixels, respectively.

The BRDF variable has been intercompared with MODIS data belonging to the collection MCD43C1 [RD-11] (*MCD43C1_BRDF_Albedo_Parameter1_Band4*) [RD-13].

The GAPMAP product versions we analysed do not present uncertainties and quality flags already, but they will be included in the final version for public distribution. Data has cloud mask already applied. A further filtering for data quality has been applied in our analysis following the GRASP team suggestions, discarding all data for which the retrieval absolute residual is above 10% (GAPMAP variable *Absolute_residual*).

Please note that not all cases are shown in the main document. The majority of plots and statistical analyses are included in the Appendix (5) in order to improve the readability of the main text.

3.1 Total aerosol optical depth (AOD)

This section details the analysis of total aerosol optical depth (AOD total), describing the emplaced methods and results obtained. We report the results for versions 0.3 and 0.4, the comparison with MODIS and AERONET data, and the improvements obtained in version 0.4 compared to the previous one.

The aerosols in the atmosphere directly scatter and absorb solar radiation, modifying the radiative energy budget, and act as condensation nuclei for clouds. Therefore, aerosols have a strong impact on air quality. The AOD is monitored via satellites and ground-based observations, and their data are assimilated into atmospheric models to improve the forecasts and improve climate impact studies. The total aerosol optical depth quantifies the extinction of light that occurs via scattering and absorption by aerosol particles, integrated over a vertical column from Earth's surface up to the top of atmosphere.

Since MODIS resolution is 10 km, GAPMAP data have been binned together to match the MODIS grid for comparison. MODIS data have been screened, selecting only the high-quality pixels (quality flag value equal to 3). As MODIS uncertainty we employ the Deep Blue algorithm uncertainty (variable *Deep_Blue_Aerosol_Optical_Depth_550_Land_Estimated_Uncertainty*), principally used for land retrievals.

3.1.1 GAPMAP AOD V0.3 data

This paragraph is dedicated to the assessment of the V0.3 that we received during the first phase of our study.

Figure 3.2 shows the GAPMAP total aerosol optical depth at 550nm at nominal resolution of 2.3 km (binned) for the four scenes. Data shows a variability that reflects the presence of the cloud mask and the terrain orography as seen in Figure 3.2C, where in the northern region of India the absence of data highlights the boundary of the Himalayan Mountain range. But all four scenes show artifacts at the right border of the scenes, presenting a defined sharp edge (see black arrows on the plots) that is probably caused by algorithm boundary issues. We also noticed in Figure 3.2 B and C a bimodal data distribution, which highlight a net division between left and right side of the image. This is particularly evident in Figure 3.2C where the left side shows total AOD values between 0 and 0.32 (blue area) while the right side appears more heterogeneous. Due to this sharp division, we suppose it is an artifact caused by the optical sensor calibration or view angles acquisition mode.

Figure 3.1 RGB images of the GAPMAP scene.

Figure 3.2 four GAPMAP total aerosol optical depth V0.3 at 550nm of the four scenes provided by GRASP.

3.1.1.1 GAPMAP AOD V0.3 vs MODIS

In this section are reported the analysis carried out between GAPMAP total aerosol optical depth V0.3 at 550 nm and MODIS *AOD_550_Dark_Target_Deep_Blue_Combined* product. Therefore, we selected the closes measurements in time over the same Area of Interest (AOI). Figure 3.3, Figure 3.4, Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6 show the comparison of GAPMAP re-gridded data (left panel) and MODIS data (right panel). These plots show the high discrepancies in measurements between the two instruments. In some cases, in GAPMAP data it is possible to identify the same features that are present in MODIS but are only small spots (black circles on plots), GAPMAP measurements do not present the same structures present in MODIS data. Such discrepancies are better highlighted by GAPMAP-MODIS difference plots in Figure 3.7. Cases 1, 2, and 3, show that the difference generally ranges between 0 and 0.225. For case 1, there is a strong dichotomy in the image: in the upper part, the bias is negative, between 0 and -0.30, while in the lower part, the difference is positive. In case 3, a clear distinction is strongly highlighted between the left and right sides (see dashed line). On the left, the difference is almost zero, whereas on the right side there is a strong positive bias above 0.45. A strong positive bias is also present in case 4, where GAPMAP overestimates the MODIS measurement roughly everywhere except along the edges. In case 2, however, the difference plot shows good agreement, with a very small difference compared

to MODIS. The scatter plots and linear regression analysis confirm the low agreement between GAPMAP and MODIS AOD measurements, correlation coefficients all range between 0.21 and 0.56 and evidencing the large variability of GAPMAP measurements, particularly evident in case 3 and 4, Figure 3.8 C and D. Table 3.1 shows a summary of scatter plots and regression analysis between GAPMAP AOD V0.3 and MODIS AOD. Finally, Figure 3.9 and Figure 3.10 present the GAPMAP-MODIS difference histograms and average bias as function of MODIS measurements. The histograms show a double pick for cases 1,3 and 4, a bimodal distribution of GRASP-MODIS difference, confirming what was already evident in Figure 3.7. The variation of average bias at varying MODIS AOD measurement suggest a negative trend for higher MODIS AOD measurement. This result could be caused by some mathematical approximations/models or conditions emplaced into GRASP algorithm for the AOD retrieval that led to a negative trend when comparing GAPMAP data with a reference dataset.

Figure 3.3 (left) GAPMAP total aerosol optical depth V0.3 at 550nm of case 1 interpolated to 10km resolution. (right) MODIS total AOD from dark target and deep blue combined at 550nm.

Figure 3.4 (left) GAPMAP total aerosol optical depth V0.3 at 550nm of case 2 interpolated to 10km resolution. (right) MODIS total AOD from dark target and deep blue combined at 550nm.

Figure 3.5 (left) GAPMAP total aerosol optical depth V0.3 at 550nm of case 3 interpolated to 10km resolution. (right) MODIS total AOD from dark target and deep blue combined at 550nm. Black circles show the highly pollutant areas detected by GAPMAP that also occurs in MODIS data.

Figure 3.6 (left) GAPMAP total aerosol optical depth V0.3 at 550nm of case 4 interpolated to 10km resolution. (right) MODIS total AOD from dark target and deep blue combined at 550nm.

Figure 3.7 GAPMAP AOD V0.3-MODIS difference plots of the four scenes analysed. The results clearly show the strong discrepancies between the two instruments.

Figure 3.8 GAPMAP V0.3-MODIS AOD scatter plots and linear regression analysis. Results show low agreement between GAPMAP and MODIS AOD data.

Table 3.1 Summary of scatter plots and regression analysis between GAPMAP AOD V0.3 and MODIS AOD for all four scenes.

Liner regression analysis results AOD GAPMAP V0.3- MODIS	q	m	Correlation Coefficient	Bias	Number of points
CASE 1	0.1311	0.49	0.50	-9.15e-02	2653
CASE 2	0.1202	0.67	0.53	1.32e-02	2771
CASE 3	0.2235	0.76	0.42	1.46e-01	13710
CASE 4	0.6178	0.46	0.21	4.69e-01	3513

Figure 3.9 GAPMAP V0.3-MODIS AOD differences histograms.

Figure 3.10 GAPMAP V0.3-MODIS AOD average bias.

3.1.1.2 GAPMAP AOD V0.3 vs AERONET

This paragraph presents the results of the comparison of AOD measurements from GAPMAP and AERONET stations, as well as MODIS AOD and AERONET stations. The AERONET network delivers different AOD Level products that differ in data quality and calibration. The AOD V3 Level 1.5 has automatic quality control (NRT) that implement cloud screening to remove optically thin cirrus contamination and quality controls to remove sensor temperature artifacts and remove AOD affected by solar eclipses and other effects. The AOD V3 Level 2 is based on Level 1.5 with pre and post calibration applied and minimal manual intervention. The L2 is preferred but not always available, so we used a combination of L1.5 and L2 AERONET dataset for the cross-comparison with GAPMAP and MODIS [RD-14]. For each scene, several AERONET stations that acquired data on that day were identified. Since AERONET measurements are local and strongly influenced by the instrument's viewing direction and wind direction, an optimal comparison was obtained by averaging the GAPMAP and MODIS pixel values within 5 km of the AERONET station, while AERONET data were averaged over a 30-minute window (± 15 minutes) around the satellite acquisition time. The uncertainty for AERONET data has been evaluated summing the standard deviation of measurements acquired during the 30 minutes temporal window and the AERONET measurement uncertainty given by [RD-15]. While the GAPMAP AOD uncertainty has been estimated by using the standard deviation of pixels within 5 km from the AERONET ground stations. MODIS uncertainty has been estimated by the square sum of the standard deviation of the pixels within 5 km from AERONET stations, and the mean value of uncertainty given for the Deep-Blue algorithm.

For each comparison the mean value, standard deviation, and number of points used for the averaging are reported. The results shown in Figure 3.11 show agreement in the four cases that generally fall within 1-2 σ .

Figure 3.11 GAPMAP V0.3 AOD and MODIS AOD data intercomparison with AERONET ground-based data.

3.1.2 GAPMAP AOD V0.4 data

This paragraph presents the results obtained with the GAPMAP AOD V0.4 that is the latest version analysed in this work. Since we received a larger number of scenes for this version, we decided to present them separately to better analysed each case. The scenes acquired on days 27/12/2023, 28/12/2023, 08/03/2024 are reprocessed cases 1,2 and 3 from V0.3. A detailed intercomparison is provided for these three scenes present in both datasets V0.3 and V0.4 to highlight improvements and main differences. A detailed analysis is reported for products over specific area as Indian Peninsula, Arabic Peninsula, Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, and Atlantic Ocean.

3.1.2.1 GAPMAP AOD V0.4 vs V0.3 data analysis

Figure 3.12, Figure 5.1 and Figure 3.19 present a comparison of cases 1, 2, and 3 acquired by GAPMAP and processed at versions V0.3 and V0.4. An improvement in the V0.4 product is evident: in all three scenes, a greater data coverage is observed, including over the sea. The edge-data issue highlighted in section 3.1.1 is less pronounced compared to V0.3. The cloud mask in V0.4 correctly filters and removes the cloud-covered areas.

For case 3, the problem of a sharp division between the right and left portions of the scene persists, indicating that further refinements are required to enhance product quality.

V0.4 products were compared with MODIS data using the same methodology applied for version V0.3. The difference plots between GRASP and MODIS measurements (Figure 3.13, Figure 5.2 and Figure 3.20, left panels) show a bias generally ranging from approximately -0.20 to 0.30, with a slightly higher positive bias for case 3 (Figure 3.20), where values range between -0.20 and 0.9, indicating a slight narrowing of the bias range relative to V0.3.

The relative difference plots (Figure 3.13, Figure 5.2 and Figure 3.20, right panels) provide additional insight into the spatial distribution of discrepancies between GAPMAP AOD V0.4 and MODIS products. For cases 1 and 3, a distinct separation within the scenes is observed: one area where the relative difference is close to 0%, and another where it exceeds 70%. For all three cases the scatter plots and linear regressions between GRASP V0.4 and MODIS data show improved agreement compared to V0.3. The correlation coefficients for V0.4 are consistently higher, highlighting the positive impact of the updates introduced in version V0.4, see Table 3.2 with summary results of linear regression.

The bias plots as a function of MODIS AOD measurements (Figure 3.15, Figure 3.17 and Figure 5.9, bottom center panel) exhibit a similar trend to that of version V0.3, with biases around 0 to 0.5 for low AOD values, gradually becoming negative as MODIS AOD increases. The histograms of the differences display a narrower peak around the mean value, representing an improvement over version V0.3, where in some cases a double-peaked distribution was observed (Figure 3.15, Figure 3.17 and Figure 5.9, upper right panel).

Table 3.2 Summary of scatter plots and regression analysis between GAPMAP AOD V0.4 and MODIS AOD for all four scenes.

Liner regression analysis results AOD GAPMAP V0.4- MODIS	q	m	Correlation Coefficient	Bias	Number of points
CASE 1	0.2384	0.58	0.54	6.18e-02	4694
CASE 2	0.1792	1.03	0.61	1.89e-01	9962
CASE 3	0.1947	0.89	0.56	1.57e-01	14094

3.1.2.1.1 Day 27/12/2023, Indian peninsula V0.4 vs V0.3 case 1

Figure 3.12: GAPMAP AOD products V0.3 (left panel) and V0.4 (right panel) relative to case 1 already showcased in section 3.1.1

Figure 3.13 GAPMAP AOD – MODIS AOD differences (left panel), GAPMAP AOD – MODIS AOD relative differences (%) (right panel) of case 1.

Figure 3.14 (left panel) MODIS AOD uncertainty, (right panel) difference uncertainty ratio related to case 1.

Figure 3.15 (left panel) scatter plot and linear regression analysis, (right panel) GAPMAP V0.4-MODIS AOD differences histograms, (bottom center) histogram of differences vs MODIS measurements, for case 1.

Figure 3.16 AOD intercomparison with ground based AERONET network for both GAPMAP V0.4 and MODIS data, (if match occurs) for case 1.

3.1.2.2 GAPMAP AOD V0.4 - Indian Peninsula region

This paragraph summarizes the results of the comparison between GAPMAP AOD v0.4 and the reference datasets over the Indian Peninsula region. Figure 3.17 shows the RGB acquisitions for the three observations, identified as A, B, and C. By comparing these images with the AOD product shown in Figure 3.18, it is evident that the cloud mask effectively filters out cloud-contaminated pixels. Products A and C still present the net division between left and right parts of the image that was highlighted in V0.3 but less evident. The difference between GAPMAP and MODIS measurements, reported in Figure 3.20, and the corresponding relative difference in Figure 3.21, indicate an improvement in the agreement between the two datasets compared to version V0.3.

Figure 5.11 shows that the MODIS uncertainty is very small and uniformly distributed across the entire scene. The ratio between the difference of GAPMAP and MODIS measurements and the MODIS uncertainty is greater than 1 in more than 50% of the image, indicating that the discrepancy between the measurements is very large and significantly exceeds the MODIS uncertainty, see Figure 5.12. The scatterplots reveal a broad variability of GAPMAP measurements relative to MODIS, which lead to an average correlation coefficient of 0.39 ± 0.10 , evaluated on an average number of paired observations of 3477 ± 685 .

The comparison with AERONET measurements is shown in Figure 5.16. In case A, GAPMAP overestimates the AOD value relative to AERONET, whereas in cases B and C, the AOD retrieved by GAPMAP is lower than both the AERONET station and the MODIS measurements, with the MODIS values being close to those from AERONET, within $\pm 1\sigma$.

Figure 3.17 RGB images of three GAPMAP acquisitions over Indian Peninsula.

Figure 3.18 GAPMAP AOD V0.4 data over Indian peninsula.

Figure 3.19 MODIS AOD data over Indian peninsula.

Figure 3.20 Differences GAPMAP AOD V0.4 – MODIS data over Indian peninsula.

Figure 3.21 Relative (%) differences GAPMAP AOD V0.4 – MODIS data over Indian peninsula.

3.1.2.3 GAPMAP AOD V0.4 – Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region

This paragraph presents the results of the comparison between GAPMAP AOD v0.4 and the reference datasets over the Mediterranean and North African regions. Figure 3.22 shows the RGB acquisitions for the three scenes, identified as A, B, and C. By comparing these images with the AOD product shown in Figure 3.23, it can be observed that the cloud mask effectively filters most clouds but appears to inadequately remove some high-altitude clouds, particularly in acquisition C, over the North African area. From the comparison with the RGB imagery, it is evident that certain geographical surface features are clearly reproduced and highlighted in the AOD product, leading to unrealistic AOD values. This effect is particularly noticeable in product A where stripes from local orography are evidenced in AOD map, and in B product the dark desert/mountainous triangular shape feature is highlighted in AOD map. Such anomalies are highlighted within the circled and triangular shapes on plots. A similar effect suggests a huge impact of the terrain albedo on the retrieved AOD values.

The MODIS measurements shown in Figure 3.24 display AOD values close to zero across the entire region observed by GAPMAP, further highlighting that the AOD anomalies detected by GAPMAP-0 are primarily linked to the orography of the area rather than to actual atmospheric AOD

signals. The difference maps reinforce this interpretation, as the differences remain near zero throughout the investigated area, consistent with the near-zero measurements, except in regions where GAPMAP-0 exhibits orographic anomalies.

The scatterplot results indicate no agreement between GAPMAP and MODIS, with correlation coefficients below 0.1 and even negative values for cases A and B (-0.02 and -0.04, respectively). In this region, GAPMAP shows a wide variability in AOD values (ranging from 0 to 2), compared to MODIS measurements (ranging from 0 to 0.5).

The comparison with AERONET measurements confirms that GAPMAP overestimates AOD relative to both MODIS and AERONET stations. At the Lampedusa site, all three datasets GAPMAP, MODIS, and AERONET are available. Here, MODIS and AERONET show an agreement within 1σ , consistent with what was observed in the Indian Peninsula region.

Figure 3.22 RGB images of three GAPMAP acquisitions over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region.

Figure 3.23 GAPMAP AOD V0.4 data over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region.

Figure 3.24 MODIS AOD data over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region.

Figure 3.25 Differences GAPMAP AOD V0.4 – MODIS data over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region.

Figure 3.26 Relative (%) differences GAPMAP AOD V0.4 – MODIS data over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region.

3.1.2.4 GAPMAP AOD V0.4 - Arabic Peninsula

This paragraph summarizes the results of the analysis of the GAPMAP AOD v0.4 product acquired over the Arabian region. The RGB image shows an acquisition almost completely free of clouds. The AOD map in Figure 3.27 (left panel) indicates that the cloud mask effectively removes the few clouds present. The comparison with the corresponding MODIS acquisition (right panel) reveals some differences between the two products: GAPMAP reports higher AOD values in the area located in the eastern part of Oman. The scatterplot in Figure 5.24 shows a better agreement compared to previous cases, with a correlation coefficient of 0.61 and a slope coefficient of $m = 1.03$, computed over 9962 paired observations. The intercomparison with AERONET stations is reported in Figure 5.25. GAPMAP AOD v0.4 overestimates the AOD value reported by AERONET.

Figure 3.27 RGB image of acquisition over Arabic Peninsula.

Figure 3.28 GAPMAP AOD products V0.4 (left panel) and MODIS AOD (right panel) relative to Arabic Peninsula case.

Figure 3.29 GAPMAP AOD – MODIS AOD differences (left panel), GAPMAP AOD – MODIS AOD relative differences (%) (right panel) of Arabic Peninsula case.

3.1.2.5 GAPMAP AOD V0.4 - Atlantic Ocean region

This paragraph summarizes the results of the analysis of the GAPMAP AOD v0.4 product acquired over the Atlantic Ocean.

The comparison between the RGB image and the GAPMAP AOD map suggests that the cloud masking is functioning correctly. Compared to the land acquisitions, the observation over the ocean shows a better agreement with the MODIS data, as also supported by the difference plots. These plots reveal a positive bias of GAPMAP with respect to MODIS. The scatterplot further confirms the good agreement, with a correlation coefficient of 0.76, a slope of 0.99, and an average bias of 0.13. For this product, the intercomparison with AERONET stations is not reported due to the absence of stations in the region. In this case the difference uncertainty ratio cannot be evaluated since the uncertainty of MODIS data is provided only over land.

Figure 3.30 RGB image of acquisition over Atlantic Ocean.

Figure 3.31 GAPMAP AOD products V0.4 (left panel) and MODIS AOD (right panel) relative to Atlantic Ocean case.

Figure 3.32 GAPMAP AOD – MODIS AOD differences (left panel), GAPMAP AOD – MODIS AOD relative differences (%) (right panel) of Atlantic Ocean case.

3.2 Bidirectional reflectance distribution function

This section details the analysis of bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF), describing the employed methods and results obtained. We obtained similar results for V0.3 and V0.4, so we report the results for version 0.4 only. GAPMAP BRDF data have been compared with MODIS data.

The GAPMAP BRDF Variable used for the analysis is *Surface_land_brdf_rossli_isotropic*.

MODIS BRDF variable used as a reference is *BRDF_Albedo_Parameter1_Band4*. MODIS data have been filtered out using quality flag, selecting high quality data (*BRDF_Quality*≤3)

The BRDF is a radiometric variable that describes surface's reflectance behaviour under directional illumination and viewing geometries. Formally, the BRDF is defined as the ratio of the reflected

radiance in direction to the incident irradiance from direction. Because surfaces in remote sensing and climate modelling seldom reflect isotropically, the BRDF provides a means to characterise angular anisotropy of reflectance, enabling corrections for view and solar-angle effects (e.g., in vegetation indices, multi-angle sensor retrievals) and computation of directional or hemispherical albedo. The BRDF variable lays an important role since many remote sensing observations of surface are made at non-nadir and non-normal illumination; thus neglecting angular effects can bias retrievals of surface reflectance, albedo, biophysical parameters, and energy-balance fluxes. [RD-16][RD-17].

The semi-empirical kernel-driven BRDF model known as the Ross-Li model (also called the Ross-Thick / Li-Sparse or reciprocal Ross-Li) was developed for large-scale land surface application, especially for satellite retrieval of albedo and directional reflectance. In this formulation the reflectance is expressed as a linear combination of three terms: an isotropic (constant) kernel, a volumetric scattering kernel derived from the canopy radiative transfer approximation of Michael Ross (Ross-Thick), and a geometric-optical shadowing kernel.

The Ross-Li BRDF model is a widely used, kernel-based parameterisation of surface directional reflectance for land surfaces, designed to capture key scattering mechanisms (volumetric and geometric) in a linear formulation, allowing the interpretation of anisotropy in terms of structural canopy and/or terrain features [RD-18].

The BRDF measurements from version 0.4 do not show significant improvements compared with version 0.3; therefore, the detailed analysis presented in this document refers only to version 0.4 data. In the Conclusions and Recommendations chapter (4), a comparison of the statistical analyses over the Indian Peninsula versus MODIS is reported for both version 0.3 and version 0.4 data to summarize the results.

3.2.1 BRDF GAPMAP V0.4 vs MODIS

This section summarizes the results of the analysis performed on the GAPMAP BRDF Ross–Li products. The analysis includes a comparison with the RGB imagery to assess the applied cloud masking, as well as a comparison with the MODIS product. The evaluation is conducted by dividing the data into geographic areas, since the different characteristics of the investigated regions may lead to different outcomes. The data are grouped into the Indian Peninsula (5 products), the Mediterranean Sea and North Africa (3 products), the Atlantic Ocean (1 product), and the Arabian Peninsula (1 product). The assessment of each group is presented in this paragraph.

The comparison of the data for the Indian Peninsula region shows that the cloud masking effectively filters clouds, in agreement with the corresponding MODIS products. GAPMAP and MODIS acquisitions are not exactly coincident in time but very close; therefore, variations in cloud masking are justified. In case 1, the BRDF values over the area are very low, ranging between 0 and 0.16, with good agreement between GAPMAP and MODIS due to the low variability in the measurements. The edge-related issues observed in the AOD products are also present in the BRDF product, visible in Figure 3.33, where a separation between left and right sides of the image can be noted. This artifact is more evident in the difference maps between GAPMAP and MODIS (Figure 3.34). The scatter plot highlights a wide variability in the GAPMAP measurements (0-0.6) compared with MODIS, whose measurement range is 0-0.15. The histogram of the differences shows a bimodal distribution with the second peak centered around 0.1. Products associated with cases 2 and 3, acquired on two consecutive days, exhibit a higher variability in BRDF values with extensive cloud coverage over the Himalayan region, which clearly divides the BRDF map: south of the mountain range values are close to zero, whereas in the northern area the BRDF increases to approximately 0.2-0.4. GAPMAP product for case 3 (Figure 5.32) shows a clear artifact on the left side of the product, an oblique discontinuity not related to geographical features. The difference maps for these two cases show small values ranging from 0 to 0.06, even in the northern areas where BRDF differs more significantly from zero. The scatter plots reveal a peculiar points distribution, with wide variability in the GAPMAP values relative to MODIS in the 0-0.1 MODIS range, and a broad points cloud for values between 0.1 and 0.5, with correlation coefficients equal to 0.37 and 0.41, respectively. The case 4 product (Figure 5.36) is cloudier than the others and

shows that the GAPMAP cloud masking has filtered most of the data. An artifact affecting the right border of the image is visible. The comparison with MODIS and the resulting scatter plot are consistent with cases 2 and 3, with a correlation coefficient of 0.39. Case 5 (Figure 5.40) clearly shows a separation between the southern part below the Himalayan range, with values close to zero, and the northern part of the image, where BRDF values range from approximately 0.15 to 0.5. The difference map highlights an artificial separation between the left and right portions of the GAPMAP image. The correlation is slightly improved in this case, equal to 0.59.

The products covering the Mediterranean and North Africa region (Figure 3.37, Figure 5.44, Figure 5.48) show better agreement with MODIS than those over India. In cases 1 and 2, the GAPMAP cloud masking almost completely removes measurements over Italy and the Balkan region, whereas the MODIS acquisition shows full coverage over the same area. The scatter plots show high correlations of 0.98, 0.86, and 0.57, respectively.

The product acquired over the Arabian Peninsula (Figure 3.41) has a correlation of 0.73 with the MODIS data. Many local BRDF features and anomalies are visible in both maps. The comparison reveals a general underestimation of GAPMAP BRDF values in the upper part of the image compared with MODIS.

Finally, the product acquired over the Atlantic Ocean off the African coast (Figure 3.45) does not allow a meaningful comparison with MODIS, since the MODIS BRDF map includes only land pixels and the region of interest contains very few measurements over the Cape Verde Islands. The number of points available for comparison is only 32, and therefore this case is not considered further.

3.2.1.1 Indian Peninsula region

3.2.1.1.1 27/12/2023 case 1

Figure 3.33 (left panel) GAPMAP BRDF product, (right panel) MODIS BRDF product over Indian peninsula, case 1.

Figure 3.34 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF differences, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF relative differences over Indian peninsula, case 1.

Figure 3.35 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF scatter-plot, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF histogram of differences over Indian peninsula, case 1.

Figure 3.36 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF average bias, (right panel) GAPMAP RGB image over Indian peninsula, case 1.

3.2.1.2 Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region

3.2.1.2.1 11/01/2024 case 1

Figure 3.37 (left panel) GAPMAP BRDF product, (right panel) MODIS BRDF product over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 1.

Figure 3.38 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF differences, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF relative differences over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 1.

Figure 3.39 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF scatter-plot, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF histogram of differences over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 1.

Figure 3.40 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF average bias, (right panel) GAPMAP RGB image over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 1.

3.2.1.3 Arabic peninsula region

3.2.1.3.1 28/12/2023 case 1

Figure 3.41 (left panel) GAPMAP BRDF product, (right panel) MODIS BRDF product over Arabic peninsula region, case 1.

Figure 3.42 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF differences, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF relative differences over Arabic peninsula region, case 1.

Figure 3.43 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF scatter-plot, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF histogram of differences over Arabic peninsula region, case 1.

Figure 3.44 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF average bias, (right panel) GAPMAP RGB image over Arabic peninsula region, case 1.

3.2.1.4 Atlantic ocean region

3.2.1.4.1 22/02/2024 case 1

Figure 3.45 (left panel) GAPMAP BRDF product, (right panel) MODIS BRDF product over Atlantic Ocean region, case 1.

Figure 3.46 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF differences, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF relative differences over Atlantic Ocean region, case 1.

Figure 3.47 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF scatter-plot, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF histogram of differences over Atlantic Ocean region, case 1.

Figure 3.48 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF average bias, (right panel) GAPMAP RGB image over Atlantic Ocean region, case 1.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this work, the GRASP GAPMAP-0 Level 2 products processed with versions 0.3 and 0.4 were analyzed, along with corresponding documentation (PUG and L2 ATBD). The analyzed data are not publicly distributed but are currently available for internal use only, with the aim of improving the geophysical retrieval and the overall data quality. GAPMAP-0 is the precursor of a constellation expected to be launched by 2030. GAPMAP-0 was an instrument mounted on a SPIRE platform hosting multiple payloads. The satellite's stability issues have affected data quality, particularly regarding geolocation accuracy and sensor's pointing.

The GRASP team is actively working at improving and refining the GAPMAP product in preparation for the future constellation. The GRASP algorithm developed and used by the team represents the state of the art for the retrieval of atmospheric, air quality, and land parameters, and it is employed by space agencies for their satellite data retrieval. The associated documentation is of high quality, with the L2 ATBD being comprehensive and detailed. The PUG was written following the example of ESA atmospheric product documentation and is compliant with ESA and international standards. Some refinements are still needed, as the product is not yet fully mature and many entries were graded Not-Assessable. For instance, the full uncertainty retrieval chain is not yet generated. In our opinion, the documentation could reach the Maturity Matrix highest scores (excellent-ideal) in all evaluation categories, once finalized.

The AOD and Ross-Li BRDF variables were compared with MODIS satellite data, and the AOD was also compared with ground-based measurements from the AERONET network. The GAPMAP AOD measurements generally agree with the reference data, within $1-3\sigma$ of AERONET observations, although they show a larger variability compared with MODIS measurements. Edge artifacts were observed in the products, which have been partially mitigated by the stray-light correction introduced in V0.4. We observed a large bias affecting AOD observations over the east Indian peninsula and a very poor agreement with MODIS reference over the north Africa. These effects are maybe due to the influence of the surface albedo on the retrieval algorithm. GRASP algorithm does not employ an a-priori constrain taking into account the surface properties of the observed area and this should strongly affect the results over high albedo area such as the Sahara Desert, as suggested by GRASP team in a mail exchange.

To quantify potential improvements between processing versions 0.3 and 0.4, average statistical analyses were performed for all products acquired over the same Area of Interest (AOI). The results over the Indian Peninsula indicate improved data quality, with better agreement with MODIS, reduced standard deviation, and more defined difference histogram for version 0.4 products.

The BRDF measurements also show general agreement with MODIS data. The edge artifacts observed in AOD are also present in the BRDF measurements, and for the products acquired over North Africa, additional artifacts appear that seem to follow geographic features. The averaged analyses of the products over the Indian region do not show improvements between versions 0.3 and 0.4, with correlation coefficients of 0.53 and 0.41, respectively. The standard deviation for version 0.4 also appears comparable to that of version 0.3, and the histogram of differences shows a slightly broader distribution, indicating that further refinements are needed for the BRDF variable.

Figure 4.1 Intercomparison of scatterplot results of AOD GAPMAP-MODIS for GAPMAP V0.3 (left panel) and GAPMAP V0.4 (right panel) averaged for products over Indian Peninsula.

Figure 4.2 Intercomparison of histogram of differences of AOD GAPMAP-MODIS for GAPMAP V0.3 (left panel) and GAPMAP V0.4 (right panel) averaged for products over Indian Peninsula.

Figure 4.3 Intercomparison of average bias of AOD GAPMAP-MODIS for GAPMAP V0.3 (left panel) and GAPMAP V0.4 (right panel) averaged for products over Indian Peninsula.

Figure 4.4 Intercomparison of scatterplot results of BRDF GAPMAP-MODIS for GAPMAP V0.3 (left panel) and GAPMAP V0.4 (right panel) averaged for products over Indian Peninsula.

Figure 4.5 Intercomparison of histogram of differences of BRDF GAPMAP-MODIS for GAPMAP V0.3 (left panel) and GAPMAP V0.4 (right panel) averaged for products over Indian Peninsula.

Figure 4.6 Intercomparison of average bias of BRDF GAPMAP-MODIS for GAPMAP V0.3 (left panel) and GAPMAP V0.4 (right panel) averaged for products over Indian Peninsula.

5. APPENDIX

In this appendix are reported all plots and statical analysis of GAPMAP v0.3 and v0.4 for AOD and BRDF variables that were not shown in previous chapters.

5.1 AOD

Figure 5.1 GAPMAP AOD products V0.3 (left panel) and V0.4 (right panel) relative to case 2 already showcased in section 3.1.1

Figure 5.2 GAPMAP AOD – MODIS AOD differences (left panel), GAPMAP AOD – MODIS AOD relative differences (%) (right panel) of case 2.

Figure 5.3 (left panel) MODIS AOD uncertainty, (right panel) difference uncertainty ratio related to case 2.

Figure 5.4 (left panel) scatter plot and linear regression analysis, (right panel) GAPMAP V0.4-MODIS AOD differences histograms, (bottom center) histogram of differences vs MODIS measurements, for case 2.

Figure 5.5 AOD intercomparison with ground based AERONET network for both GAPMAP V0.4 and MODIS data, (if match occurs) for case 2.

Figure 5.6 GAPMAP AOD products V0.3 (left panel) and V0.4 (right panel) relative to case 3 already displayed in section 3.1.1

Figure 5.7 GAPMAP AOD – MODIS AOD differences (left panel), GAPMAP AOD – MODIS AOD relative differences (%) (right panel) of case 3.

Figure 5.8 (left panel) MODIS AOD uncertainty, (right panel) difference uncertainty ratio related to case 3.

Figure 5.9 (left panel) scatter plot and linear regression analysis, (right panel) GAPMAP V0.4-MODIS AOD differences histograms, (bottom center) histogram of differences vs MODIS measurements, for case 3.

Figure 5.10 AOD intercomparison with ground based AERONET network for both GAPMAP V0.4 and MODIS data, (if match occurs) for case 3.

Figure 5.11 MODIS AOD uncertainty maps over Indian peninsula.

Figure 5.12 Ratio between differences GAPMAP AOD V0.4 – MODIS data and MODIS uncertainty over Indian peninsula.

Figure 5.13 Scatter plot and linear regression analysis for GAPMAP AOD V0.4 and MODIS AOD data, over Arabic peninsula.

Figure 5.14 GAPMAP AOD V0.4 – MODIS AOD differences histograms, for Indian peninsula.

Figure 5.15 GAPMAP V0.4-MODIS AOD differences histograms vs MODIS AOD measurements over Indian peninsula.

Figure 5.16 AOD intercomparison with AERONET ground-based network data over Indian peninsula.

Figure 5.17 MODIS AOD uncertainty maps over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region.

Figure 5.18 Ratio between differences GAPMAP AOD V0.4 – MODIS data and MODIS uncertainty over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region.

Figure 5.19 Scatter plot and linear regression analysis for GAPMAP AOD V0.4 and MODIS AOD data, over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region.

Figure 5.20 GAPMAP AOD V0.4 – MODIS AOD differences histograms, for Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region.

Figure 5.21 GAPMAP V0.4-MODIS AOD differences histograms vs MODIS AOD measurements over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region.

Figure 5.22 AOD intercomparison with AERONET ground-based network data over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region (scene B only).

Figure 5.23 (left panel) MODIS AOD uncertainty, (right panel) difference uncertainty ratio related to Arabic Peninsula case.

Figure 5.24 (upper left panel) scatter plot and linear regression analysis, (upper right panel) GAPMAP V0.4-MODIS AOD differences histograms, (bottom center) histogram of differences vs MODIS measurements, over Arabic peninsula.

Figure 5.25 Intercomparison of GAPMAP AOD v0.4 acquired over Arabic Peninsula with AERONET network data.

Figure 5.26 (left panel) MODIS AOD uncertainty.

Figure 5.27 (upper left panel) scatter plot and linear regression analysis, (upper right panel) GAPMAP V0.4-MODIS AOD differences histograms, (bottom center) histogram of differences vs MODIS measurements, over Atlantic ocean case.

5.2 BRDF

Figure 5.28 (left panel) GAPMAP BRDF product, (right panel) MODIS BRDF product over Indian peninsula, case 2.

Figure 5.29 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF differences, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF relative differences over Indian peninsula, case 2.

Figure 5.30 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF scatter-plot, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF histogram of differences over Indian peninsula, case 2.

Figure 5.31 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF average bias, (right panel) GAPMAP RGB image over Indian peninsula, case 2.

Figure 5.32 (left panel) GAPMAP BRDF product, (right panel) MODIS BRDF product over Indian peninsula, case 3.

Figure 5.33 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF differences, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF relative differences over Indian peninsula, case 3.

Figure 5.34 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF scatter-plot, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF histogram of differences over Indian peninsula, case 3.

Figure 5.35 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF average bias, (right panel) GAPMAP RGB image over Indian peninsula, case 3.

Figure 5.36 (left panel) GAPMAP BRDF product, (right panel) MODIS BRDF product over Indian peninsula, case 4.

Figure 5.37 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF differences, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF relative differences over Indian peninsula, case 4.

Figure 5.38 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF scatter-plot, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF histogram of differences over Indian peninsula, case 4.

Figure 5.39 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF average bias, (right panel) GAPMAP RGB image over Indian peninsula, case 4.

Figure 5.40 (left panel) GAPMAP BRDF product, (right panel) MODIS BRDF product over Indian peninsula, case 5.

Figure 5.41 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF differences, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF relative differences over Indian peninsula, case 5.

Figure 5.42 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF scatter-plot, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF histogram of differences over Indian peninsula, case 5.

Figure 5.43 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF average bias, (right panel) GAPMAP RGB image over Indian peninsula, case 5.

Figure 5.44 (left panel) GAPMAP BRDF product, (right panel) MODIS BRDF product over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 2.

Figure 5.45 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF differences, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF relative differences over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 2.

Figure 5.46 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF scatter-plot, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF histogram of differences over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 2.

Figure 5.47 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF average bias, (right panel) GAPMAP RGB image over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 2.

Figure 5.48 (left panel) GAPMAP BRDF product, (right panel) MODIS BRDF product over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 3.

Figure 5.49 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF differences, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF relative differences over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 3.

Figure 5.50 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF scatter-plot, (right panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF histogram of differences over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 3.

Figure 5.51 (left panel) GAPMAP-MODIS BRDF average bias, (right panel) GAPMAP RGB image over Mediterranean Sea and North Africa region, case 3.

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